

Smart Automatic Newspaper Vending Machine Controller IC

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Abstract: A machine, used for dispensing items like snacks, beverages, lottery tickets, etc to customers automatically meaning without manual intervention is referred to as a Vending Machine. Vending Machines are part of life in most of the major cities in India and across the globe. The objective of this paper is design a Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC. The input to this machine is currency in Indian rupees and it delivers the product to the costumer. This controller is an IC and has 22 pins in total, 15 pins are for input and 7 pins are for output. User can enter currency up to two digits, select one product, if user wants his currency back before getting the product by the machine then by pressing the 'CANCEL' button he can get refund. This machine has unique property it takes the picture of that person who inserts the currency in it. The Verilog code for the proposed this Smart Automatic Newspaper Vending Machine Controller IC is developed and simulated in 'ModelSim SE PLUS 6.5'.

Keywords: FSM; Verilog HDL; Vending Machine;

I. Introduction: The use of Vending Machine by human civilization is not new. According to historical facts in 1st century Vending Machine was used to dispense the holy water [04]. Coin-operated machines that dispensed tobacco were being operated as early as 1615 in the taverns of England. These machines were portable and made of brass [08]. An English bookseller, Richard Carlile, devised a newspaper dispensing machine for the dissemination of banned works in 1822. Simeon Denham was awarded British Patent no. 706 for his stamp dispensing machine in 1867, the first fully automatic Vending Machine [10]. But these all machines were based on mechanical systems. The concept of Finite State Machine was developed by Edward F. Moore in 1956. After this Vending Machines were become faster and easier to operate [06].

Nowadays all the computational works inside a Vending Machine is performed by a controller IC. Vending Machine controller IC based on the principle of 'Finite-State Machines'. A finite-state machine (FSM) or finite-state automaton, or simply a state machine, is a mathematical model of computation used to design both computer programs and sequential logic circuits [12]. The machine is in only one state at a time; the state it is in at any given time is called the current state. It can change from one state to another when initiated by a triggering event or condition; this is called a transition. A particular FSM is defined by a list of its states, and the triggering condition for each transition [11].

There are various methods of designing the Vending Machines are discussed in [02], [03] and [09]. Also in [05] the passenger's requirements for ticketing system are given. In [07] a coffee Vending Machine is designed using single electron encoded logic (SEEL). The designed circuit is tested and its power and switching time is compared with the CMOS technology. The process of running this Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine can be understood as: First step is $RST = 1$, it will make 'next state pin' (pin ns) at state zero (000000). Then $RST = 0$ it will make next state equal to the present state (value of pin ns = ps). Now enable one pin among a, b, c, d, e. (these are currency pins). Enabling these pins means customer has put the currency (in two digits) into the machine. Enabling currency pin (a, b, c, d, e) will also enable the 'pic' pin which will enable the camera for one or two cycle. But in this Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine enabling the currency pin is not enough to get the output so we also have to enable

‘product enable pin’ (product pins: ue, ve, we, xe, ye). These product pins indicate to the newspapers like Dainik Jgran, Hindustan Times, Hindu, Dainik Bhaskar and Times of India. Then as an output customer will get newspaper according to his choice.

The paper is divided into five sections. In section II we describe the whole process of designing the Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC. Section III caters light on the result and discussion with schematic diagrams. Proceeding ahead, section IV derives the conclusion. The paper ends in the section V giving the references of the work.

Fig.1: FSM (Finite State Machine flow) diagram.

II. Design of controller IC:

In this Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC there are ‘14’ states. At first enable the restart pin (rst=1) this will push next state (n.s.) to state 0. Then after running it one clock cycle put it at rst=0 this process will put the present state and next state at state 0. Then inserting the currency (a, b, c, d) in this machine will push F.S.M. into the next state (state1, state 2, state 3... state n) as seen in Fig.2. If the desired newspaper is available then it would be delivered to the customer. After delivering the newspaper the machine will come to its initial state (state 0). The figure no.2 explains this concept.

Fig.2: F.S.M. flow model for the Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC.

There are 22 pins in this controller IC 15 pins are for input and 7 pins are for output. The pin description with pin diagram of the IC is given below.

01: Currency Pins (a, b, c, d, e): There are 5 currency pins present in this IC. Every Currency Pin indicates a certain amount of currency. We can define the value of each pin through programming.

02: State Pins (n.s., p.s.): These are two state pins present state (p.s.) pin and next state (n.s.) pin. These pins are used to define the different states in Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC.

03: Product Enable Pins (ue, ve, we, xe, ye): In a Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC entering currency is not enough. To get a newspaper customer must enable these pins.

04: Re-start Pin (rst): This pin is use to restart the program or process.

05: Clock Pin (clk): Through this pin we apply the wave pulses on program. Here in this program we are applying Negative edge pulses. It means other pulse will be activated only when clock pulse goes down.

06: Cancel Pin (cancel): This pin is used to cancel the ordered newspaper, enabling this pin puts the whole program in rst=1. It means customer will get no output.

07: Output Pins (u, v, w, x, y): These five pins are used as output pins. Any one of the product pin is high it means newspaper has delivered to the user. Every pin indicates a newspaper as Dainik Jgran, Hindustan Times, Hindu, Dainik Bhaskar, and Times of India.

08: Picture Pin (pic): This pin enables automatically when currency pin is enabled by the user and disables after one or two cycle. This pin enables the camera, which takes the picture of user instantly.

09: VCC: This is for the power supply.

Fig.3: Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC

The procedure of operating the Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine can be understood by this flow chart diagram.

Fig.4: Flow diagram of Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC

III. Result and Discussion:

The procedure of getting product from this Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine can be defined in five easy steps as given below.

Step.01. -Enable RST = 1, it will put the 'next state pin' (pin ns) at state0.

Step.02. - Then RST = 0 it will make next state equal to the present state (value of pin ns = ps).

Step.03. - Now enable the one pin among a, b, c, d, e. (these are currency pins). It means customer has put currency into the Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine, putting the

currency into the machine enable the pin 'pic' which will enable the camera attached with the Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine.

Fig.5: Process of Enabling the camera when one currency pin get activated.

Step.04. - Enabling the currency pin is not enough to get the output we also have to enable 'product enable pin' (product pins: ue, ve, we, xe, ye). Then newspaper will come out. Fig.5 shows the process of getting output.

Fig.5: Wave Forms of getting product 'u'.

Step.05. - If anyone wants his currency back before getting the product then, he only has to press the button 'CANCEL' pressing this button will stop the all process and by some mechanical method in Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC will return the currency as shown in fig.7

Fig.7: Wave Forms of cancelling the product before getting it.

IV. Conclusion:

In previous time Vending Machines has no any option to get the remaining currency so it was necessary for users to put the certain amount of currency (coin) into the Vending Machine. In present time we have facility to get back remaining currency. But these Vending Machines have a problem that if customer wants his currency back before getting product then it is not possible. Using this Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine Controller IC customer can get his currency back before getting newspaper. But it is necessary for him to enable the pin 'cancel' by pressing the button 'CANCEL' before getting the product otherwise it would not be possible. There is also a unique feature of this Vending Machine; this Smart Automatic News Paper Vending Machine is equipped with a camera which takes the picture of every customer who uses it.

Applications:

We can use these machines in those places where too much vendors are not allowed like railway stations, metro stations, and other overcrowded places. This can also be used by secret agencies to track suspicious persons by using camera information.

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